

ISic3658

Fragment of a Greek inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

stone

Object

base

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

trench (1956) on west side of Temple A

Coordinates

38.000628, 14.261263

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME30588

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 5.7 cm

Width 18.5 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

painted

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-4: 6-10 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. []Σ[] []Q[]P[]

2. []Τ,ΙΛΩΟ

3. []ΑΓΜΔΑΡΥΗ

4. Ι[]ΤΑΘΑΓ[]

Apparatus

Text from Prag-Tigano 2017

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 318 no.12b

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.2

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